

A COMPARATIVE HISTORICAL APPROACH TO NEW MEDIA: RADIO, TELEVISION, AND MOBILE DEVICES IN TURKEY

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ABSTRACT

Introduction

This paper is an extended version of the presentation delivered at the “6th International Mardin Artuklu Scientific Research Conference” in June 2021. The paper is based on the research funded by the European Commission’s Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Widening Fellowship and it has three parts. The first part describes the research project and the historical and scholarly background through which the research questions have emerged. The second part details the methods used in order to answer these questions. The third and the final part introduces some initial findings of the project. So far, the major finding of the research project is that technology users have been approached as active producers well before the expansion of digital platforms. During the age of radio in the 1920s and 1930s, radio listeners were also addressed as active producers. Based on this finding, the paper concludes by asking a new question: How do we see the capacity to produce that is attributed to the users of technology has changed from the early 1900s to the early 2000s?

Keywords: History of new media, digital media, radio

I. Description of the Project

This project historically traces the ideas about new media technologies in Turkey by focusing on three major periods: 1920s and the early 1930s when radio was first introduced in Turkey; 1950s and the early 1960s; when television first started its broadcasts; and the 2000s, our current era, when mobile devices has become widespread. While tracing this history, the research builds on the scholarly approaches that move beyond limiting new media to digital media and suggest that each medium was new at the moment of their introduction.¹ This study approaches new media as a historical concept and turns it into an analytical tool to understand the interaction between global political-economic dynamics and people’s constructions of the newness of new media. It then traces how these constructions of new media change as these political economic dynamics change.

There is a relationship between Turkey’s dominant mode of economic production and features attributed to new technologies. Here, the mode of economic production refers to the shift we have been observing globally since the 1970s; from industrial-developmental economy to neoliberalism. An example of this comes from the 1950s when television was a novelty in Turkey. In this period, there were worries about productivity if television had turned into a new medium of entertainment. An article on the Milliyet Newspaper, that appeared on January 24, 1953 was a case in point.² The article first explains the amazement around television by underlining how this new device merged radio and cinema. Then the author continues by stating his worries about productivity in an age defined by television. He suggests that unlike radio,

¹ Gitelman, L. (2006) *Always Already New: Media, History, and the Data of Culture*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press; Manovich, L. (2001) *The Language of New Media*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

² “Karaköy’de Seyredilen Televizyon Neşriyatı,” *Milliyet*, 24 Ocak 1953, Sayfa 2.

television requires one to sit in front of it with full attention and prevents one from focusing on the tasks one needs to finish. Television requires the attention of both “eyes and ears,” making it impossible for people to enjoy it while also doing some household tasks.

The project questions the relation between these worries about productivity and the dominant mode of capital accumulation of the era, that is industrial-developmental. One of the main features of industrial-developmental mode of accumulation was its emphasis on production. With the shift to neoliberalism, consumption habits became much more visible, while production was rendered more invisible albeit it continued to form the backbone of capital accumulation. The study questions if these worries about productivity, shaped around television, were informed by the dominant mode of economic accumulation of the era—that is, the production oriented industrial developmentalism. It then contrasts this situation to the current era of neoliberalism when consumption became much more visible and how this informs the constructions of media novelty. Early research on the use of mobile devices in Turkey in the 2000s highlights that owning the most recent version of mobile devices has become an important sign of upward mobility for lower classes.³ Hence, the new technology in the neoliberal era was adopted as a sign of class status through its consumption—not through its links to productivity. Drawing on these changing constructions of media novelty vis-à-vis economy, the project examines how neoliberalization turned newness of mobile devices into tools that foster particular styles of (conspicuous) consumption whereas in an earlier economic mode, productivity was the major concern that rendered a medium new.

The overall research questions of the project are: 1) As new political economic conditions transform gender, class based, and global inequalities, how do these newly reframed hierarchies make visible a medium’s novelty? 2) How does this perceived novelty inform the ways that lower and middle classes, different gender groups, and state officials use new technologies to challenge or reproduce inequalities?

II. Methods

For both radio and television, the project focuses on a time period before each of these mediums were nationalized and came under the direct control and sponsorship of the state. In so doing, the research aims to better understand the very first conceptions about what made radio and television new in the early days of these devices. For the radio, this was the period between 1927 and 1936 when the Telsiz Telefon Türk Anonim Şirketi (Turkish Radio Telephone Company) or by its acronym TTTAŞ was the only responsible actor for producing radio content. Archival research was carried out in the Cumhuriyet and Milliyet newspapers’ website and radio periodicals published in the late 1920s and early 1930s, such as Telsiz, Radyo Amatör, Ses, Radyo Programı were collected.

For television, the project similarly focuses on the period before the state-owned Turkish Radio and Television Company, TRT was founded in the 1950s and the 1960s. In 1952, a television station was established by İstanbul Technical University, namely, İTÜ TV. For almost ten years İTÜ TV aired television content to a limited number of viewers mostly living in İstanbul. Here, in addition to newspaper research, periodicals such as Radyo-Televizyon Elektroteknik, Resimli Radyo (Radio with Pictures), Televizyon, and Renkli Televizyon (Colored Television) were collected. There are also oral history interviews conducted with people who know the founders and producers of İTÜ TV.

For the mobile devices part, the research includes digital ethnography of Instagram. Here, the project focuses on different gender and class groups’ uses of digital media by exploring women

³ Özcan, Y.Z. and Koçak, A. (2003). A need or a status symbol? Use of cellular telephones in Turkey. *European Journal of Communication* (18):241-254.

who became Instagram famous. There is a particular group of women who started their Internet journey by blogging about their motherhood experiences. They then turned to Instagram, as the platform became much more widespread. The online content they produced about motherhood had the purpose of challenging the perfectionist motherhood myth, that put women into a position of an endless giver to their infants. These women mostly posted their failures, challenges in the process of raising a kid. A closer look at these women reveal that they are highly educated, or has cultural capital, with prestigious high school diplomas and university degrees. Hence, the project compares these women's Instagram use with that of lower-class women's Instagram use. Ethnographic data, will examine how women use social media—in relation to their class position—in order to navigate new economic hierarchies of the neoliberal era both in their homes and outside. The research asks how different classes' navigation of new technologies inform the ways that digital media is constructed as new in the 2000s.

III. Initial Findings: How to Make Your Own Radio

Archival research into the radio magazines of the 1930s reveal that radio listeners in this era were not addressed as passive receivers. Major radio magazines, such as *Radyo Alemi*, *Ses*, included detailed instructions about how to build a radio at home so they addressed their listeners as builders or producers of the very technology of radio. *Radyo Alemi* magazine, for example,

Radyo Alemi Magazine – August 5, 1934

Ses Magazine – September 4, 1932

had a section devoted to the amateurs in which the editors explained how people could build crystal detectors, which were essential for building radio. This section continued to detail other basic parts necessary for radio building in its next volumes. Another radio magazine, *Ses*, similarly included information on how to build bobbins and other technical parts of the radio device.

Given the economic conditions of the era, it makes sense for radio magazine publishers to teach ways for building a radio. Radios were usually very expensive luxury items only the upper classes could afford. In fact, a list of radio owners in Turkey in 1935 revealed that radio owners were mostly living in upper class neighborhoods of the country's urban areas.⁴ In order to reach out to lower classes, teaching how to build a radio was essential. In so doing, radio magazines of the early 1930s addressed their followers not as passive receivers but as builders or producers who were capable of building their own machines.

⁴ Kocabaşoğlu, U. (2010) *Şirket Telsizinde Devlet Radyosuna: TRT Öncesi Dönemde Radyonun Tarihsel Gelişimi ve Türk Siyasal Hayatı İçindeki Yeri*. Ankara: İletişim.

If we compare this with digital media—the new media of the contemporary moment—we see that especially with the expansion of social media platforms, we are now also talking about users who are no longer simple consumers but also active producers. There are even new names attributed to the users of digital media, such as prosumer—that emphasizes this intensified aspect of media production. A quick research into the early days of the radio, however, reveals that radio listeners in this era were not addressed as passive receivers either. Radio listeners in the 1920s were also approached as active producers, not maybe as content producers—as is the case in digital media—but as builders who can put together the radio machine itself. This situation complicates today’s well-established perception of digital platforms as the first venues that turned people into active producers—or prosumers. Comparing people’s such responses to new technology in different periods permits us to dismantle ideologies surrounding digital media and endows us with the capacity to ask more compelling research questions, such as: How do we see the capacity to produce that is attributed to the users of technology has changed from the early 1900s to the early 2000s?

In today’s digital media world, users’ capacity to produce is usually attributed to the content itself. They are not very frequently approached as builders of technology as it was the case during the times of radio. Technology for digital media users is rather something users can only “mess with” to a certain extent. Freidrich Kittler, for example, in one of the early accounts of digital technology suggests that “the apparent ‘user-friendliness’ of commercial software and systems is achieved at a cost,” as “pre-defined ‘priorities, prohibitions, privileges and handicaps’” “burnt into the kernel of the system” in such a way that “they are immune to user intervention or ‘hacking’, and place restrictions on what the user may or may not alter or even see: ‘one can no longer examine the operands of the operations.’”⁵

Here, I read Kittler’s explanation as a symptom of the changing ideologies surrounding technology with the rise of digital media. With digital media, users may create their own content and that makes them active producers but they are also very much bounded by the limits of the operating systems of digital technology. Software often “hides a whole machine from its users”⁶ and explaining how this machine is built is no longer an area of interest. From the times of radio when the magazines invited their listeners to understand the intricacies of machine building and encouraged them, quite directly with titles such as “you yourself can build your own bobbins,” we see a shift toward a new understanding of technology where one can mess with a working machine only to a certain extent. This rough comparison shows us that in the times of radio, users were also approached as producers—as builders of machines themselves, even if not the content. And today, users are approached mainly as content creators. In other words, creative capacity of technology users lays not anymore in their ability to build machines. The creativity is rather attributed to the content creation itself.

⁵ Kittler, F. (1997) *Literature, Media, Information Systems*. Amsterdam: G+B Arts, p.158.

⁶ *Ibid.*, p.158.